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**The Impact of Genetics and Optical Technology on Neural
Stem Cells and Neurological Diseases: a Review**

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Abstract

In the past few years, there has been a significant increase in attention to the application of genetics and light-based materials in the field of neurology to increase the success of the treatment of diseased neurons. Optical technologies and experiments performed on laboratory animals, including mice, significantly have attracted attention in this field. Increased attention to NSCs stems from their capacity to improve the development and efficacy of therapeutic agents used in neurology. This study examines subsequent outcomes mainly relying on NSC and optical technology assessments of neuronal and genetic disease. In addition, it provides a thorough review of the techniques used to assess neural stem cells. The primary objective of this survey is to give a source of inspiration for approaches to cure brain diseases such as MS using genetically related cells based on neural cells. This article analyzes and reviews the impact of genetics and optical technology on neural stem cells and neurological diseases.

Keywords: *Genetics, Neural Stem Cells, MS, Optical Technologies*

Introduction

Stem cells possess the remarkable capability to transform into various types of cells and have the ability to generate identical copies of themselves. Under optimal circumstances or appropriate stimuli, they can lead to the emergence of a plethora of distinct cell types, which constitutes the entirety of the organism. Stem cells have immense therapeutic capability to treat the injuries and illnesses within the human body (P De Miguel et al., 2010).

Two distinct categories of pluripotent stem cells found in mammals are embryonic stem cells, known as ES cells, which are obtained from the internal cellular cluster of blastocysts, and embryonic germ cells, known as EG cells, which are resulted from embryos that have undergone implantation. These remarkable stem cells own the capacity to undergo differentiation into a diverse array of specialized types of cells, enabling the formation of diverse organs and tissues within the body. Furthermore, apart from embryonic stem (ES) and embryonic germ (EG) cells, stem cells which are specific to certain tissues can be extracted from different tissues at more advanced phases of development. These tissues include bone marrow mesenchymal, hematopoietic and neural stem cells, among others (Yang et al., 2017).

The presence of multipotent neural stem cells (NSCs) has been well-documented in the developing and central nervous system (CNS) tissues of adult rodents. The mentioned cells own the remarkable ability to proliferate continuously and possess the ability to differentiate into multiple cell types or exhibit various functions. They transform into three primary cell types of the central nervous system (CNS): astrocytes, neurons, and oligodendrocytes (Duan et al., 2008).

Neural stem cells (NSCs) have been observed in both embryonic cells and the adult human brain, demonstrating their capacity to transform into various types of cells. A study was carried out that specifically targeted a cohort of individuals suffering from cancer, who were administered bromodeoxyuridine (BrdU) infusion for the purpose of diagnosis and subsequently passed away (Amirbekyan et al., 2023).

This particular study revealed the presence of proliferating cells labeled with BrdU, which also exhibited co-labeling with a neuronal marker, in the granule cell layer within the dentate gyrus of the hippocampus. This study provides clear evidence that the adult human's central nervous system (CNS) undergoes a continuous creation of new neurons (Hassouna, Wüstefeld, et al., 2016).

Why are neural stem cells (NSCs) fruitless in brain repair in cases of neurodegenerative illnesses or following central nervous system (CNS) damages? There are several factors that could explain why adult NSCs are unable to effectively repair the injured brain: (a) despite the presence of NSCs, their quantity falls short in facilitating brain repair, (b) the NSCs demonstrate a lack of ability to reach the location of the pathology, and (c) the microenvironment within the pathological site does not provide a conducive environment for the expansion and reparative function of NSCs (Kim, 2007 & 2004).

The challenges associated with repairing the brain could potentially be resolved by delivering an ample quantity of NSCs alongside a concurrent environment rich in trophic factors to the site of injury. The recent transplantation experiments involving the employment of a cell line derived from human neural stem cells which possesses conditional immortality in various models of neurological diseases, demonstrate the practicality of this approach (Kim, 2007 & 2004).

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Stem cells have distinctive characteristics as they possess the remarkable capability to self-renew and transform into diverse cell types. They own immense potential in the treatment of injuries and ailments in humans. There exist two distinct classifications of stem cells with pluripotent characteristics, namely embryonic stem cells and embryonic germ cells, which possess the capability to generate a wide range of organs and tissues (Zakrzewski et al., 2019; Shevde et al., 2012; & Rajabzadeh et al., 2019).

Furthermore, stem cells that are unique to specific tissues can be detached from diverse tissues during distinct phases of development. It is widely acknowledged that multipotent stem cells of the neuron are present in both the growth and central nervous system of adult rodents. These stem cells offer potential for the advancement of novel therapies targeting disorders and conditions that impact the nervous system (Zakrzewski et al., 2019; Shevde et al., 2012; & Rajabzadeh et al., 2019).

In general, stem cells hold great promise as a field of study that has the capacity to transform the field of medicine and enhance the quality of life for numerous individuals. As the research in this particular domain progresses, it is highly probable that novel and groundbreaking therapies will be formulated, drawing upon the distinctive characteristics exhibited by stem cells (Hoang et al., 2022).

Stem cells, in simpler words, are unique cells with the remarkable capability to generate various types of new cells. Consequently, they hold the potential to be employed in the treatment of injuries and illnesses in the human body. There exist two primary classifications of stem cells, namely embryonic stem and embryonic germ cells, which have the capability to differentiate into a wide range of organs and tissues. Stem cells have very large potential in the advancement of novel therapies, and continuous research endeavors are being conducted in this domain to unravel their capacity in enhancing the overall human health and well-being (Zakrzewski et al., 2019).

Stem cells possess remarkable versatility and great potential as a formidable asset in the realm of medicine. Their unique capability to generate novel cells and tissues holds promise for therapeutic purposes, aiding in the process of healing and restoration. Scientists are persistently investigating the characteristics and prospective uses of these entities, aiming to exploit their medicinal capabilities for the betterment of individuals seeking treatment (Zakrzewski et al., 2019).

Clonally Detached Human Neural Stem Cell Lines with Stable Immortality

Introduction of oncogenes has resulted in the development of NSCs' immortalized cell lines, which have been continuously dividing in recent times. These immortalized NSC lines own favorable properties for fundamental investigations on neural advancement as well as cell replacement treatments or gene therapy researches. Firstly, the NSC cell line can be rapidly expanded in culture, reaching large numbers within a short period of time (24-36 hours doubling time). Secondly, the NSC cells exhibit homogeneity as they originate from a single clone. Lastly, these NSC lines allow for stable expression of therapeutic genes (Kim, 2007 & 2004).

The Determination of Cell Fate in Neural Stem Cells

Multipotent neural stem cells (NSCs) have long been acknowledged to exist in the developing or central nervous system (CNS) tissues of adult mammals, including humans. These

cells have the remarkable ability to proliferate indefinitely and exhibit pluripotent capabilities, enabling them to undergo differentiation into the three primary cell types that are present in the central nervous system: astrocytes, neurons, and oligodendrocytes. Nevertheless, the spontaneous occurrence of NSCs differentiating into neurons and glial cells takes place when they are cultivated on permissive substrates (Okano, 2010).

Neural Stem Cell-Based Treatment for Lysosomal Storage Illnesses

The introduction of cell replacement and gene transplantation techniques to treat the damaged or diseased central nervous system (CNS) has opened up new possibilities for the advancement of promising and effective therapeutic/remedial approaches for a wide range of neurological disorders in humans. These disorders encompass stroke, neurodegenerative conditions like “Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and Alzheimer's disease, along with lysosomal storage diseases” occurring in infants (Shihabuddin & Cheng, 2011).

Neural Stem Cell-Based Therapy for Stroke

In Japan, Korea, and China, stroke is the leading cause of death and ranks second in terms of mortality. There exist two primary classifications of stroke, namely ischemia and intracerebral hemorrhage. Abrupt and nearly complete cessation of blood flow to the brain, known as ischemic stroke, results in ischemic alterations in both the striatum and cortex. This ultimately leads to a persistent sensorimotor impairment in the long run. After the onset of a stroke, there is limited potential to restore the functions that were present before the damage occurred. Despite the existence of various neuroprotective agents, their effectiveness in reversing the effects of a stroke is minimal (Li Y, Zhang, 2021).

Cell Therapy for Parkinson's Disease

Parkinson's disease (PD) is an appealing objective for these therapeutic strategies due to the well-documented degeneration and demise of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra. Previous research has documented that the transplantation of fetal ventral mesencephalic cells into the caudate and putamen regions of patients with Parkinson's disease resulted in a significant enhancement in the patients' clinical progression. Nevertheless, this particular therapeutic technique has encountered significant constraints due to ethical considerations (Björklund & Lindvall, 2017).

Proactive Stem Cell Therapy in Huntington Chorea or Disease

Huntington's chorea or disease (HD) is an inherited neurodegenerative condition which follows an autosomal dominant pattern. It is distinguished by the presence of involuntary choreiform motions, a decline in cognitive abilities, and disruptions in emotional well-being. The cause of Huntington's disease is still mostly unknown, and the exact processes that lead to its development are not yet completely understood, despite the discovery of the HD gene and its corresponding protein. This lack of understanding hinders the development of desired therapeutic interventions for HD. The utilization of fetal human brain tissue transplantation could potentially offer a valuable approach in mitigating neuronal harm within the brain affected by HD (Reiner, Dragatsis, & Dietrich, 2011).

Neural Stem Cells Therapy for Brain Tumor

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Glioblastoma multiforme, a type of malignant brain tumor, continues to pose a significant challenge in terms of treatment options and survival rates, even with the utilization of extensive surgical removal, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy. Their resistance to therapy is linked to their remarkable migratory behavior and capacity to infiltrate effortlessly and extensively into healthy brain tissues, frequently traveling significant distances away from the main tumor masses (Rong & Zhang, 2022).

Malignant gliomas, particularly glioblastomas, are frequently detected during the later stages of the disease. The rapid advancement of the disease is evident as it swiftly transforms into a life-threatening condition, even with the implementation of rigorous treatment protocols. At the time of the initial surgical assessment, the majority of malignant gliomas, especially primary glioblastomas, already demonstrate significant variations in histologic and cellular characteristics, diffuse infiltration affecting the brain, necrosis, and hemorrhage (Rong & Zhang, 2022).

The histopathological features serve as the sole diagnostic standard for identifying this particular type of tumor. Understanding the sequence in which they emerge during the development of a tumor can enhance our comprehension of disease advancement and facilitate the adjustment of therapeutic approaches (Rong & Zhang, 2022).

Despite the establishment of numerous preclinical models for malignant gliomas, the traditional xenograft models of cell lines exhibit restricted heterogeneity and invasiveness. Additionally, these models demonstrate varying degrees of pathological similarity to gliomas in humans. Novel animal models have been created employing glioblastoma stem cells that were obtained from surgical specimens of humans in recent times (Slika et al., 2023).

Additional models, incorporating genetically modified neural stem cells (NSCs) and neural precursor cells, i. e., progenitor cells (NPCs), were also generated. These novel models exhibit a higher degree of resemblance to tumors found in humans. Nevertheless, despite the advancements made, the systematic analysis of early-stage glioblastoma features is often hindered by persistent challenges such as lengthy latency periods, varying penetrance rates, technical intricacies, and limited reproducibility (Suzuki et al., 2022).

Moreover, in order to facilitate disease advancement monitoring, it is crucial for glioblastoma models to demonstrate an invasive tumor growth within the adult brain in the background of an immune-competent microenvironment. By inducing brain tumor-initiating cells (BTICs) from adult murine NSCs, we successfully developed a syngeneic mouse model that uniformly and accurately reproduces the characteristic traits of glioblastomas (Zeng et al., 2021).

Based on our examination of tumor advancement in this model, it appears that the initial step in disease progression and growth is the movement of individual tumor cells to the healthy brain. Subsequently, the host's reaction occurs, leading to the appearance of abnormal cells and the development of a tumor (Zhao & Yan et al., 2021).

After various antibodies, which target cell surface antigens, were used to screen dissociated human fetal brain cells, a population of neurosphere-forming NSCs that were positive for CD133 was identified. These CD133-positive NSCs made up 4% of the total cell population. The CD133-positive cells underwent expansion and subsequent differentiation into both neurons and glial cells (Peh et al., 2009).

Different groups of researchers were also able to extract neural stem cells (NSC) from the brain tissues of adult individuals. The adult human hippocampal tissues acquired during the surgical procedure for epilepsy were subjected to enzymatic dissociation and subsequently cultivated in a serum-containing medium. Neurospheres were constituted by the surviving cells, and upon being plated onto substrates, the production of neurons and glial cells occurred (Hattiangady et al., 2020).

The nervous system is constructed by two primary cell types: glial cells and neurons which play an active role in the transmission of electrical signals and the processing of information. Glial cells surpass neurons by a significant margin in all regions of the nervous system, constituting a substantial portion of the nervous tissue. For example, approximately 50% of the brain's volume is occupied by glial cells. These cells perform numerous essential tasks, both in the process of growth and development, as well as in the regular functioning of the fully developed system (Araque & Navarrete, 2010).

The central part of nervous system (CNS) is composed of glial cells and neurons that originate from neural precursor cells found in a germinal layer known as the ventricular zone. This ventricular zone lines the lumen of the developing spinal cord as well as the ventricles of the brain. The realization of oligodendrocyte advancement is more comprehensive in the spinal cord compared to the brain. Oligodendrocytes in the cord seem to arise from a highly limited region within the ventricular zone. This process is contingent upon the presence of transcription proteins or factors, i. e., Olig 1 and Olig 2, as well as a signaling molecule (Araque & Navarrete, 2010).

During brain development, neurons often originate far away from their final position within the cellular framework. Advancement thus encompasses a significant degree of neuronal migration, wherein glial cells assume a pivotal function. Extensive examination has likely been conducted on the cerebral mantle or cortex and the cerebellum, making them the focus of comprehensive studies. The previously stated radial glial cells play a crucial role as essential frameworks for the extensive migration of neurons, which involves the participation of astrotactin and neuregulin-1 (Rahimi-Balaei et al., 2018).

Multiple Sclerosis (MS)

This specific condition has been recognized by Lucchinetti and Lassmann (2001) as the disease most widely associated with glial cells. Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a degenerative condition characterized by a notable immune system involvement, primarily targeting oligodendrocytes. Multiple lesions are formed in the central nervous system (CNS) leading to the destruction of myelin and the death of oligodendrocytes. Axons are additionally impacted in a negative manner. The etiology of MS is not comprehensively understood, and the development of an efficacious treatment is still pending (Lucchinetti & Lassmann, 2001).

The experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) rodent model has been widely employed to elucidate the mechanisms underlying autoimmune inflammation in multiple sclerosis. Immunization against myelin antigens may not precisely replicate the underlying mechanisms of disease initiation in humans. However, the evaluation of the effectiveness of a potential multiple sclerosis treatment in various EAE models frequently serves as an important indicator of its applicability to the human context (Robinson et al., 2014).

Numerous therapeutics that have been examined in patients with multiple sclerosis are actually founded on principles extracted from EAE information. In the context of multiple sclerosis, we are confronted with a pathological condition that relies on the movement of immune cells and the production of cytokines. This implies that there exist several potential avenues for therapeutic intervention throughout the progression of the disease (Amedei, Prisco & D'Elios, 2012).

Initially, efforts can be undertaken to impede the initial growth of the harmful or pathogenic population. Secondly, the movement of cells towards the site of inflammation may experience hinderance. Finally, the molecules responsible for effecting change that are generated by this particular group can be rendered ineffective. To disclose the exact molecular mechanisms behind pathogenicity, it is essential to discover a therapeutic target that is involved in any of these stages or to mitigate the side effects caused by therapy with a specific medication. We will explore several models employed to investigate the underlying mechanisms of autoimmunity and to devise therapeutic interventions (Chen et al., 2017).

From Rats to Mice

Rats were the favored laboratory animals for studying MS until the 1980s. Their popularity may have originated from their status as one of the initial models employed as laboratory animals for scientific experimentation, which may result in this particular model functioning effectively.

Compared to mice, rats possess the superiority of their larger size, which facilitates working with their central nervous system (CNS). This is particularly beneficial as it allows for relatively straightforward techniques to isolate and analyze the spinal cord and brain. Furthermore, when compared to mice, conducting transplantation-based *in vivo* experiments or intravital microscopy is significantly more convenient (Hickman et al., 2017).

Among the various strains of rats, the Lewis rats are widely favored for conducting experiments related to experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE). The induction of the disease in Lewis rats is remarkably consistent and relatively uncomplicated. The absence of reliance on pertussis toxin for disease manifestation is advantageous, as it better replicates the human scenario in terms of disease induction (Hickman et al., 2017).

Rats that have been vaccinated with myelin basic protein (MBP) or any of its dominant peptides exhibit symptoms of the disease within approximately 10 days, provided that the antigen is mixed with complete Freund's adjuvant (CFA) (Frausto et al., 2007). An alternative method for inducing EAE in rats involves the stimulation of myelin-specific T cells through immunization with a neuroantigen in complete Freund's adjuvant (CFA), subsequently leading to the expansion and activation of these T cells in a controlled laboratory environment; upon activation, these T cells have the capability to elicit experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) in naïve animals (Frausto et al., 2007).

The manifestation and appearance of EAE in Lewis rats is characterized by a sudden onset of symptoms followed by a spontaneous healing and improvement, mirroring the recurrence of clinical signs observed in multiple sclerosis. Nevertheless, the absence of demyelination in Lewis rats is a distinctive characteristic, which sets them apart from humans with multiple sclerosis (Shin, Ahn & Matsumoto, 2012).

Moreover, the inflammation observed in Lewis rats is primarily confined to the spinal cord, which stands in stark contrast to multiple sclerosis. Hence, the model's usability has to some extent hindered its appropriateness. In addition to experiencing acute inflammation following immunization with MOG-derived peptides, Brown Norway and DA rats also exhibit demyelination in the central nervous system (Denic et al., 2011).

In aggregate, the acute EAE observed in rats does not serve as a comprehensive representation of MS. Instead, it functions as a resilient model that allows for the meticulous examination of the fundamental mechanisms implicated in T cell-mediated neuroinflammation (Constantinescu et al., 2011).

Given the aforementioned justifications, rats continue to be a favored selection as a model for MS. Nevertheless, during the 1980s, mice gradually replaced rats. Mice, due to their smaller size, are more cost-effective, enabling researchers to conduct a greater number of experiments and repetitions. Consequently, numerous contemporary reagents were produced specifically for mice rather than rats (Constantinescu et al., 2011).

The advent of flow cytometry brought about a significant transformation in the field, which was further complemented by the development of monoclonal and polyclonal antibodies that target specific cellular surface antigens in mice (and humans). In contrast, a smaller number of antibodies were specifically designed for rat antigens in the context of flow cytometry (Phelps, Pazos-Castro & Urselli et al., 2024).

The emergence of significant advancements in immunology, particularly the identification of numerous novel cytokines and elucidation of their roles, coincided with the era when mice were the prevailing choice for laboratory experimentation. Consequently, the emphasis changed to the development of reagents specifically designed for mice, rather than rats. Nowadays, utilizing mice as EAE models is considered more advantageous and efficient in terms of practicality and productivity (Masopust, Sivula & Jameson, 2017).

Neural stem cells possess innate migratory and tumor-seeking characteristics, making them a promising avenue for the therapeutic intervention of tumors which are invasive. The NSC operates as a mode of transportation specifically engineered to target and distribute gene-based therapeutic agents across various locations within tumors (Bagó, Sheets & Hingtgen, 2016).

In a prior investigation, it was shown that mouse C17.2 NSC, which possess the cytosine deaminase (CD) gene responsible for activating a pro-drug that promotes oncolysis, were able to disperse within the primary tumor site when implanted either directly into it or at a distant location such as the opposite hemisphere or peripheral vasculature. Following the administration of the prodrug 5-Fluorocytosine into the animals, there was a significant 80% decrease in the size of the resulting tumor mass (Kosztowski, Zaidi & Quiñones-Hinojosa, 2009).

The results obtained from studying NSCs derived from mice were further applied to investigate NSCs derived from humans in models of intracranial glioma and metastatic neuroblastoma in nude mice. Nude mice were subjected to an intracerebral transplantation of human glioma or an intravascular administration of human neuroblastoma through injection. After a period of 3 months, the presence of glioma mass in the cerebrum or neuroblastoma metastases in the liver and ovary were successfully established (Aboody et al., 2013).

The LacZ enzyme marker was utilized to label the human neural stem cell line, i. e., the HB1.F3 cell line, which was subsequently administered via injection into a blood vessel located in the tail of an animal, i. e., the tail vein. After administering F3 NSC through tail vessel or vein injection, the animals were euthanized at different time intervals. Subsequently, the organs and tumor were collected and subjected to histological processing (Aboody et al., 2013).

The findings suggest that these human NSCs have the ability to specifically target glioma in the brain or neuroblastoma metastases in the liver and ovary, while showing minimal accumulation in unaffected organs. The investigation is currently underway to explore the delivery of therapeutic agents, specifically the oncolysis-promoting pro-drug activating enzyme CD gene (Aboody et al., 2013).

The integration of optics, genetics, and bioengineering has paved the way for the exploration of intact neural circuits through appearing strategies. The ability to perform optical imaging and genetically target specific cell types have been significantly enhanced by the brisk advancement of interdisciplinary "optogenetic" techniques. In this investigation, we delve into significant recent progress that combines optical and genetic methodologies. Our focus is on the emergence of promising strategies that enable groundbreaking studies on neural dynamics and behavior, as well as offer new insights into well-established model systems (Rivnay et al., 2017; Cehajic-Kapetanovic et al., 2023; & Bansal et al., 2023).

Optogenetic method integrates the precise targeting of particular neurons or proteins through genetic manipulation with the utilization of optical mechanism to visualize or manipulate these targets within fully functional and living neural circuits. This method has its origins dating back several decades (Stuber & Mason, 2013). Ramon y Cajal, through the utilization of Golgi stains, recognized the significance of labeling individual neurons as he meticulously examined single neurons within intricate neural networks via histological analyses. The emergence of integrated optical/genetic techniques has enabled scientists to observe genetically specific neurons in live animals and monitor and manipulate electrical and biochemical processes within specific cell types (Ramón, & Cajal, 1909).

The development of optogenetic techniques has encompassed the progress of various methodologies: (1) fluorescence microendoscopy techniques, such as one- and two-photon imaging, which enable the visualization of fluorescently labeled cells located deep within the mammalian brain, (2) the concurrent visualization of functional brain maps in mammals and tracking the real-time changes in the structure of neocortical cells through genetic targeting, (3) using the genetically targeted reporters to visualize biochemical activity within live neurons at the subcellular level, (4) employing the transgenic mouse methods to genetically modify the biochemical function in neurons that are marked with fluorescent indicators within the intact circuitry of mammals, (5) the ability to control neural activity in behaving *Drosophila* through the use of genetically targeted optical techniques, and (6) the capacity to manipulate electrical activity in mammalian circuits using high-speed, genetically targeted optical monitoring. In this analysis, amidst the progress made in these six domains, we emphasize the significance of the fourth area and delve into the prospective future implementations of this particular technology (Mohanty & Lakshminarayanan, 2015).

The manipulation and imaging of individual neurons within intact circuits through genetic means monitoring the biochemical activity in genetically targeted neurons that express fluorescent

markers can be achieved through the implementation of an optogenetic method, which serves as a valuable complement to imaging biochemical activity (Kim, Adhikari & Deisseroth, 2017).

A novel labeling technique has emerged in recent times, which effectively accomplishes the desired objective. It permits the implementation of genetic modifications in a particular set of neurons situated in normal/healthy tissue. To summarize, this methodology is similar to a functional genetic variation of the Golgi stain (Venken, Simpson & Bellen, 2011).

Numerous strains of transgenic mice have been produced, wherein GFP serves as a marker for specific groups of neurons. This enables meticulous monitoring of various cellular activities, including axonal guidance, dendritic growth, and synaptic dynamics, on a cell-to-cell basis. The attainment of this outcome was accomplished through the utilization of a potent neuron-specific promoter known as Thy1, in conjunction with a transgenic occurrence referred to as "position effect variegation." (Feng et al., 2000).

This phenomenon leads to the labeling of neurons with varying levels of sparsity across different strains of transgenic mice, as demonstrated by (Feng et al., 2000 & Young and Feng, 2004). Incorporating a functional-genetic element, the introduction of CreERT2, a tamoxifen-responsive variant of the Cre recombinase, has been implemented in the identical cells alongside the fluorescent protein through the utilization of two instances of the Thy1 promoter (Fig. 2A) (Feng et al., 2000 & Young and Feng, 2004).

The combination of the Thy1–yellow fluorescent protein (YFP)/CreER approach offers a unique method for conditional gene knock-out or expression using the cre/loxP system. Additionally, it provides a Golgi-like fluorescent labeling of neurons, enabling the visualization of their morphology (Fig. 2B, C) (Young, Qiu, Wang, Zhao, Gross & Feng, 2008).

The manipulation of genes is limited to specific regions of labeled neurons and can be regulated over time by administering the activating medication tamoxifen. As a result, (to label individual neurons using inducible Cre-mediated knock-out), these animals have been classified as "SLICK" mice. Tamoxifen administration can effectively induce LacZ expression exclusively in YFP-positive neurons by crossing SLICK mice with a line of Cre reporter mice, where LacZ expression relies on Cre-mediated excision of a loxP-flanked transcription stop cassette (Fig. 2) (Arias, Manubens-Gil & Dierssen, 2022; Karl et al., 2006).

Performing genetic manipulation and visualizing at the individual neuron level becomes feasible in mouse models with limited labeling and significant distance between labeled neurons. There are many benefits to the accurate manipulation of neurons that have been genetically labeled (Karl et al., 2006; Venken, Simpson & Bellen, 2011).

Initially, the utilization of fluorescent labeling resembling the Golgi apparatus enables the examination of intricate morphology and synaptic links of distinct mutant neurons. Secondly, by restricting genetically-done manipulation to a specific set of or identified neurons, the examination can be conducted within a mostly unchanged neural network. This method effectively avoids significant disruption to neural circuits and allows for distinguishing between the independent functions of genes within cells and the indirect effects of deleting genes throughout the entire network. Thirdly, the SLICK system's capacity to trigger genetic manipulation enables the study of gene functionality in later developmental stages or adult organisms. This beneficial characteristic helps overcome potential obstacles related to embryonic lethality, early

developmental abnormalities, or compensatory mechanisms that may occur when a specific gene is absent. Ultimately, neurons labeling in the SLICK mice with YFP is fundamental (Sakaguchi, Leiwe & Imai, 2018).

As a result, untreated animals provide a valuable resource of labeled wild-type neurons, which can serve as control samples for genetically manipulated cells. It should be feasible to observe and analyze the characteristics of neurons *in vivo* by utilizing *in vivo* imaging techniques on YFP-labeled neurons located in accessible regions of the nervous system. This methodology facilitates the investigation of neuronal characteristics both prior to and subsequent to a genetic alteration, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the impact of a particular gene on the identical neuron in its natural setting (Young et al., 2008; Marinković, Godinho & Misgeld, 2015).

The contemporary amalgamation of optical methodologies could potentially result in a more comprehensive set of tools for conducting causal investigations on the functions of distinct genes and cells within operational neural circuitry. Hence, the combined utilization of light for imaging and manipulating identified circuits will significantly enhance our synthetic comprehension of the fundamental principles governing neural computation (Fred et al., 2020).

Apart from neural stem cells (NSCs), neurons can also be derived from various other cell types, including embryonic stem (ES) cells, embryonic germinal (EG) cells, bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells, and umbilical cord blood hematopoietic stem cells. The combination of optogenetics, genetically targeted photostimulation, or biochemical-control techniques with the emerging fluorescence imaging modalities holds great promise for *in vivo* applications (Galli et al., 2003; Casarosa et al., 2014).

This integration presents a particularly fascinating avenue for further exploration. Despite the fact that Ramon y Cajal's (1909) findings regarding neural function were primarily based on inference, the contemporary integration of optical methods could potentially provide a more comprehensive set of tools for conducting causal investigations into the functions of particular genes and cells within operational neural circuits (Delgado-García, 2015; Rossini et al., 2019).

Hence, the combined utilization of light for imaging and manipulating identified circuits will significantly enhance our synthetic comprehension of the fundamental principles governing neural computation. In the forthcoming years, it is advisable to conduct investigations on the utilization of optical techniques and precise identification of diseased cells, along with their impact on neurological disorders like multiple sclerosis (MS), while abstaining from the utilization of mice and laboratory animals (Jorgenson et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2020).

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